

The effects of loss of function mutations over adaptive trajectories in *S. cerevisiae*

In order to understand evolution, we need to understand the complex relationships between biological systems and fitness. This is a difficult task, because there are an enormous number of possible genetic states, and the mutations underlying these states interact non-additively to produce fitness. We can frame this problem by thinking of evolution as a process occurring on a high-dimensional map between this space of genetic possibilities and the fitness of each possibility, a function often referred to as the “fitness landscape.” As a population adapts to a particular environment, it moves between neighboring genotypes, constrained by the force of selection to follow paths of increasing fitness. By understanding the general properties of the fitness landscape, we can answer questions about the functional nature of a biological system - *If a mutation knocks out this gene, what effect will that have on fitness?* - and ask broad theoretical questions - *Is evolution predictable, or does it depend on chance events?*

The growing field of experimental evolution provides an avenue for addressing these questions by empirically testing important features of the fitness landscapes of microbes. We now know that in the budding yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, the effect of a beneficial mutation depends on the fitness of the genetic background where it arises [1], but whether a similar pattern holds for deleterious mutations is an open question. Deleterious mutations may be common in populations due to environmental changes or population bottlenecks, and they provide a novel way to study adaptation and to test the role of contingency in evolution. **In my PhD research, I will study the fitness landscape of *S. cerevisiae* by investigating the interplay between deleterious mutations and adaptation.** I will complete my PhD research in Dr. Michael Desai’s lab at Harvard University, where I am uniquely situated to conduct work that combines genetics, experimental evolution, and deep sequencing.

Aim 1. Changes in the fitness effects of loss of function mutations over adaptive trajectories

Given that most loss of function (LOF) mutations are deleterious, competing models make different predictions about how their effects should change with increasing population fitness. The Desai lab recently found that in *S. cerevisiae*, the fitness effect of a beneficial mutation in a particular genetic background is primarily predicted by the fitness of the background, creating a pattern of “diminishing returns” during adaptation [1]. If this “global epistasis” model holds for all mutations, deleterious mutations should also become less deleterious as the population becomes more fit. In contrast, Fisher’s geometric model predicts that the fitness effect of some mutations will change from negative to positive at different levels of adaptation [2]. I will use transposon mutagenesis and sequencing fitness assays (Tn-seq) to measure the fitness effects of a large set of loss of function mutations in populations with different initial fitness backgrounds.

Hypothesis: I predict that, in accordance with the global epistasis model [1], LOF mutations will be less deleterious in populations with higher fitness. *Methods:* First, I will evolve 24 *S.*

cerevisiae populations in standard liquid media for 1000 generations (100 days), following a similar protocol to [3]. I will freeze samples every 250 generations to create a “frozen fossil record” of each population as it adapts and gains fitness. At each of the five timepoints in this record, I will unfreeze my populations and use Tn-seq to systematically probe the fitness effects of a large number of LOF mutations. As shown in the figure at right, Tn-seq consists of two steps. In A, I transform a gene disruption library into the population, causing a diverse set of single insertion mutations. In B, I track the frequency of each mutation over 30 generations using deep sequencing of a barcode region in the insertion

[4]. Using this method, I can determine the fitness effect of every mutation in parallel by analyzing the change in its frequency [3,4]. I will create my DNA-barcoded transposon (Tn) gene disruption library using genomic DNA from *S. cerevisiae* [3], and by sequencing this library, I will associate a unique barcode with each gene disruption. These associations will allow me to connect my data to specific genes, yielding additional biologically relevant information about how *S. cerevisiae* adapts to laboratory conditions.

Aim 2. Adaptation after disruption of the genetic system

Evolution often involves transient environmental changes that alter selection pressure or population size, both of which can lead to the fixation of mutations that are not beneficial in the organism's primary environment. Do these events affect long-term outcomes of evolution? The dynamics of adaptation after a population has been "bumped" off of its adaptive trajectory are not well understood, but they have the potential to distinguish between models of adaptation. For fitness landscape models in which mutations interact only additively, any deleterious mutation simply slows adaptation. However, in "rugged" fitness landscape models where mutations interact non-additively, it is possible that deleterious steps can lead to exploration of a previously inaccessible part of genotype space, potentially allowing a population to ultimately reach higher fitness. I will capitalize on the Tn-seq method to distinguish between these models by evolving "disrupted" populations alongside "undisrupted" populations and comparing their fitness trajectories. **Hypothesis: I hypothesize that deleterious mutations will be more likely to improve evolutionary outcomes in poorly adapted populations, as predicted by [5]. Therefore, I predict that disruption due to Tn insertions will lead to higher final population fitness relative to the undisrupted populations only when the original disruption occurs at early time points from the frozen fossil record.** An alternate prediction is that disruption will slow adaptation in all cases, which would support additive landscape models. **Methods:** I will propagate "Tn-disrupted" populations from Aim 1 for 500 generations. I will measure mean population fitness every 100 generations in these populations and at the corresponding timepoints in the "undisrupted" populations using standard fluorescence-based competitions [1].

Intellectual Merit

My project aims to connect ideas about the dynamics of adaptation on fitness landscapes to a functional understanding of how a model organism changes as it adapts. Using massively parallel, sequencing-based fitness assays, this project will provide unprecedented resolution of the functional changes a population experiences during adaptation, and through evolution of Tn-disrupted clones, this study will test basic questions about the fitness landscape of evolving *S. cerevisiae*.

Broader Impacts

We now know that large asexual populations, in the form of pathogens or cancer cells, are involved in over a quarter of deaths worldwide [4]. While my research is centered on basic science questions, these basic principles of asexual adaptation are an important part of building models of how these diseases progress. I will publish my work in peer-reviewed journals aimed at a scientific audience, but I will also use the power of animations and interactivity to make my evolution research come alive on my web site, where it can be shared with the general public. As detailed in my personal statement, I will also use science communication and video to empower young people to pursue STEM careers by showing them the human side of research.

[1] Kryazhimskiy S *et al.* 2014. *Science* 344: 1519-1522. [2] Fisher RA. 1930. Clarendon Press, Oxford, U.K.

[3] Van Opijnen T *et al.* 2009. *Nature Methods* 6: 767-772. [4] Levy SF *et al.* 2015. *Nature* 519:181-186.

[5] Nahum JR, *et al.* 2015. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 112:7530-7535.

As I look back on the trajectory of my life, from a kid running around in the mountains, to an aspiring filmmaker, to a budding scientist, to a graduate student, I can't quite describe what forces pushed me in each direction. While the path of a weightless elephant on a frictionless surface can be described by deterministic forces in a few dimensions, the complex systems of this world - in science and in our lives - involve trajectories that fly, jerk, and jump through a high-dimensional space of possibilities, following rules that are difficult to discern.

As a freshman in high school, I never dreamed of being a scientist. Instead, I had two loves: making videos and exploring the natural world. When I wasn't filming, animating, or editing music videos to my favorite songs, I was outside. Every summer, my family would go on multi-day rafting trips in the desert southwest, and I would occupy my time hiking through side canyons, chasing lizards and marveling at tarantula hawks. I had vague dreams of combining my two passions by working for National Geographic and making Planet-Earth-style television that combined footage of amazing creatures with inspiring modern music.

When I started at Dartmouth College, I was surprised to find myself drawn to some of the subjects - math, computer science, and biology - that hadn't captured my attention at my rural public high school. I was fascinated by the idea of relating abstract ideas about algorithms to evolution, the process responsible for the animals that had mesmerized me as a kid in those desert canyons. These new interests were put on hold when one of my dreams was realized at the start of my junior year: I got an internship at National Geographic TV (NGTV) in Washington DC. At NGTV I worked on several shows centered on amazing and "weird" animals around the globe, transcribing footage, editing initial string-outs, and researching facts about the animals for the hosts. The opportunity to work at NGTV was incredible. I learned about technical aspects of television production and about how to write an engaging story for a particular audience. At the same time, I didn't like how the shows presented scientific knowledge as a body of concrete facts, rather than the result of the complicated and messy process of hypothesis testing. I felt, and still feel, that the public should understand that what we know about the world is the product of human inquiry based on uncertainty and doubt. By the end of my internship I had realized that while I love filmmaking, my true passion is science.

Research in the Tropics (Dartmouth Ecology Foreign Study Program, Costa Rica)

A month after finishing my internship at NGTV, I found myself crouched beside a trail at La Selva Biological Station, measuring the walking speed of leaf-cutter ants. I was working on one of 8 short studies I would complete on the Ecology Foreign Study Program (FSP) to Costa Rica. That night my partner and I measured the ants and the loads (pieces of leaves) they carried so that we could model the efficiency of the colony, trying to determine what size load a particular ant should carry to optimize its leaf mass per hour of activity. I wasn't learning *facts* anymore; I was trying to discover and understand *principles* underlying what I saw in nature, and I was hooked. The idea of pursuing science as a career became more real when I returned from the FSP and published a paper, which focused on an unusual avoidance behavior in *Eciton* army ants confronted by *Nasutitermes* termites, in the Dartmouth Undergraduate Journal of Science [1].

Southern Pine Beetle Research and Outreach in New Jersey (Ayres Lab, Dartmouth)

The next summer, I worked in Dr. Matt Ayres' lab in the New Jersey pinelands, studying the southern pine beetle (SPB), a forest pest that can kill entire stands of trees during outbreaks. I spent hours leaning over a microscope identifying SPB as well as predators and competitors from traps collected over the past several years. I helped to create a record of the population dynamics to identify what precipitates the increase in SPB numbers that leads to an outbreak. My work contributed to the ongoing development of an alternate attractors model that the Ayres Lab uses

to describe the dynamics of SPB population sizes [2].

At the same time, I was working on a series of blog posts, short videos, and one longer documentary about the SPB, a science communication project for which I received a Northern Forest Internship Grant. I set out to tell a story that would interweave narratives about the science and the societal impact of this tiny pest. While SPB research was founded in response to timber losses, it grew into a field where researchers study basic questions about ecology, outbreak dynamics, and pheromones. Faced with recent SPB outbreaks in the forests we cherish, policy makers are turning to this research to find new ways to control these pests. After spending months researching, filming, and interviewing SPB experts, I wrote a script that focused on this positive feedback loop between basic science and societal applications. I spent the fall editing the final film and published it online [3]. From my work on the SPB film, I learned about the importance of basic research, and I realized that science stories are most engaging when they are connected to human stories.

Computational Research on Microbe Evolution (Zhaxybayeva Lab, Dartmouth)

My senior year I shifted my focus towards evolutionary biology and joined Dr. Olga Zhaxybayeva's lab, where I wrote custom Python scripts to test hypotheses about evolution and ancestry using microbial DNA and protein sequences pulled from online databases. In the first part of the year, I examined evolutionary histories of the putative genes from a recently discovered bacterial virus and an associated selfish genetic element, work that resulted in co-authorship on a paper in *Environmental Microbiology* [4].

Next, I worked on the functional characterization of a hyperconserved protein (HCP) found in some marine cyanobacteria. Our collaborators had experimentally determined that HCP might interact with a ribosomal protein, so we looked for patterns of evolution in the protein and ribosomal RNA. For a clade with HCP, and a sister clade without HCP, I calculated information content at each site in multiple alignments of the ribosomal protein and rRNA sequences, and projected the results onto the 3D and 2D structures of the molecules using heat maps. This visualization revealed both conserved regions and compensatory sites that experienced many substitutions. While the information profiles weren't enough to convincingly show where HCP might interact with these molecules, these observations proved valuable because they provoked new questions about how these molecules evolve, prompting directions for future research. The results of the HCP study are now published in *PLoS ONE* [5]. My time in the Zhaxybayeva lab gave me the confidence to pursue a career in science, and deepened my interest in the details of evolutionary processes.

Broader Impacts

TIS Science Symposium

In my senior year at Dartmouth, my classmates and I started an informal science symposium at my house. The symposium was social and relaxed, and presenters were encouraged to share not just results, but also stories of the trials and tribulations that occurred throughout the research process. We were stunned by the response. For the rest of the year, we had undergraduates, graduate students, and professors presenting to a living room packed with science and non-science majors alike. What started from a simple desire to discuss cool science in an informal atmosphere became a place for a diverse group of students from all over campus to get a glimpse into how interesting and fun science can be.

Undergraduate Research Videos

During my senior year, I also created two videos in collaboration with the biology department in which senior undergraduates explained their research projects alongside footage of

research in action and animations of theoretical concepts. These videos now loop on a television in the biology building at Dartmouth as part of an effort to make independent research seem approachable to younger undergraduates who hadn't considered it a possibility.

Digital Lab Teaching and Scapes Website Project

After graduating, I spent a year at Dartmouth working in "The Digital Lab," teaching workshops on digital art and communication. I was amazed by how challenging it was to create lesson plans and teach classes, but I ultimately found it extremely rewarding. During this time, I also built a website project called "Scapes" to teach others about a specific science concept that interests me - the fitness landscape. The site features interactive JavaScript figures that convey high-dimensional data in a more realistic way [6], and a blog that provides a more accessible introduction to this complex topic in evolutionary biology. My work on Scapes deepened my interest in science education, and provided an opportunity to theoretically explore some exciting open questions in evolutionary biology.

Current and Future Work

While working independently on Scapes, I applied for PhD programs, and this summer I started my doctoral studies in Dr. Michael Desai's lab at Harvard University. I am committed to continuing to work on science communication and outreach projects at Harvard. I am currently involved in BioSketch, a new online video library where Harvard undergraduates, graduate students, and professors will explain important scientific concepts to the public in the context of their research. In collaboration with other students and the Bok Center for Teaching and Learning, I will shoot and edit videos for BioSketch that connect abstract scientific ideas to human stories, promoting the idea that science is approachable and fun. I am also training to act as a volunteer gallery guide at the Harvard Museum of Natural History, where I can directly share my passion for science with the general public and with students from the greater Boston area who visit on school trips. When working with these students, I will promote the idea that careers in science are fun and are possible regardless of one's background.

Intellectual Merit

My previous research experiences have uniquely prepared me to ask important questions about evolution from a theoretical and ecological perspective. Throughout my research career, I have designed effective experiments, collected data, and tested hypotheses statistically. This summer in the Desai lab, I learned the experimental evolution and sequencing techniques I will use in the future. My PhD research will test questions about the fitness landscape of adapting *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* populations, examining functional changes and contingencies in evolution. This research will have broad theoretical significance as well as relevance to models of the evolution of large, asexual populations of pathogens or cancer cells.

Looking Forward

While I still occasionally find myself listening to a song and dreaming of the perfect video to match it, I spend more time dreaming of being a professor who teaches undergraduates, graduate students, and the general public about the amazingly complex process of evolution. With the help of the NSF Graduate Research Fellowship, I will start to make strides towards this dream. In the lab, I will ask the kinds of questions that I have been thinking about for years - *how do biological systems work, and how does that affect their evolution?* Outside the lab, I will use my filmmaking and teaching experience to communicate about scientific concepts and to portray science as an approachable, human endeavor that anyone can enjoy.

[1] Kessler, B, **Johnson M** et al. 2013. DUJS 13S: 40-42. [2] Martinson, SJ et al. 2013. *Population Ecology* 55: 95-106. [3] www.beetlekill.wordpress.com [4] Lossouarn, J ... **Johnson, M** et al. 2015. *Environmental Microbiology*. [5] Whidden, C ... **Johnson, M** et al. 2014. *PLoS ONE* 9:e109327. [6] www.milosjohnson.com/Scapes/NK

Intellectual Merit Criterion

Overall Assessment of Intellectual Merit

Excellent

Explanation to Applicant

This is a potentially transformative project that will examine the impact of genetic background on deleterious mutations in yeast. The methods involve utilizing experimental evolution, creating a frozen fossil record, and utilizing Tn-seq to measure the fitness effects of large numbers of loss of function mutations. The researcher has excellent background and will be working in a research group with more than adequate resources to complete this project.

Broader Impacts Criterion

Overall Assessment of Broader Impacts

Very Good

Explanation to Applicant

The intellectual significance of this project is very important. This is why the lack of attention to outreach and education associated with it was so disappointing.

Summary Comments

This is an excellent research project, however lack of attention to broader impacts weakened my enthusiasm.

Intellectual Merit Criterion

Overall Assessment of Intellectual Merit

Excellent

Explanation to Applicant

Strengths: This applicant has field work experience in Costa Rica, including work on evolutionary histories and functional characterizations. The proposed research in this application includes the combination of experimental and theoretical work. Weaknesses: No major weaknesses identified.

Broader Impacts Criterion

Overall Assessment of Broader Impacts

Very Good

Explanation to Applicant

Strengths: The track record of this applicant includes interesting science communication outlets, including an internship with National Geographic, the creation of videos, and digital workshops. Weaknesses: This proposal would be strengthened with more information on goals and how to reach audiences that are traditionally underrepresented in STEM. The past track record is really great, what would make this application stronger is more focus on future efforts and plans (I think a misstep of this application is space wasted describing some efforts that aren't as impactful (e.g. the informal science symposium) and running out of room).

Summary Comments

This proposal includes exciting work that combines experimental and theoretical work in the research. This applicant appears to

be well prepared to carry out the research and the broader impact experience of this applicant is interesting. While this applicant has experience with reaching audiences through digital media, it would be interesting to flesh out how this applicant's BI work would reach underrepresented STEM audiences.

Intellectual Merit Criterion

Overall Assessment of Intellectual Merit

Excellent

Explanation to Applicant

This proposal is original, test clear hypotheses and has a high chance for success based both on the recommendation and the history of success in the Desai lab at Harvard. I consider the proposed project to be original and potentially transformative. He has excellent letters of support from both microbiologists and an ecologist.

Broader Impacts Criterion

Overall Assessment of Broader Impacts

Excellent

Explanation to Applicant

With a year spent at Dartmouth teaching workshops on digital art and communication, he has both a history and high potential to reach a broad audience in a way that is original and effective.

Summary Comments

This project has excellent potential to test hypotheses relevant to adaptive landscapes and has high potential for successful broader impacts utilizing animations and interactivity.